

Volume 9, Number 1, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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JOURNAL'S CONTACTS

Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

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DISTANCE – FROM –LEACH PIT AND QUALITY OF SHALLOW GROUNDWATER IN SELECTED WARDS OF ILORIN SOUTH LGA, ILORIN, NIGERIA

Balogun, Yekeen Idowu
Kwara State College of Education, Oro
bilqisbalogun1@gmail.com

Abstract: *Shallow wells remain a major source of water in cities. This study, examined the distance of wells to leach pit and it also compared the level of compliance of these distances to the best practices. Water samples were collected and subjected to laboratory analysis to ascertain the quantum of contamination. A total of 50 water samples were collected in two tranches of 25 samples. Each of the well water was randomly sampled within 5 geographical locations in the 11 wards of the study area. Two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), regression analysis and factor analysis were deployed in this study. Results indicated that bacteriological parameters of total coliform and bacteria counts exceeded the maximum level of drinking water quality and were generally affected by distances to leach pit as they increase towards the control sites. There was no fecal coliform growth except in well 1 in Okaka ward. This implies that while the fecal coliform level was generally satisfactory, both the total coliform and bacteria counts were unsatisfactory. In addition, there was no correlation ($r > 0$) between the depth of the water source and quality of water. In Akanbi ward, the total viable and coliform counts the values increased or decreased irrespective of distance. Nitrate ion was of high concentration throughout the samples. The study showed that there is strong correlation between bacteriological properties of water and distances which decreases in concentration with distance. Other physiochemical properties indicated no correlations with distance to leach pits. The study recommended the adoption of a scientific distance between shallow wells and soak-away pits in the study area.*

Keywords: Quality, Leach pit, Groundwater, Exploitation, Pollution

INTRODUCTION

Water crisis is a major problem in Ilorin South. The digging of wells and drilling boreholes without recourse to considering the possible implications of its distance to leach pits is common. It is very doubtful if a vast majority of consumers of underground water mainly from wells and boreholes are aware that there exist guidelines before it could be dug or drilled. The essence of the regulatory guidelines (though, largely unenforced) was to limit

exposure to microbial pollution of this important source of water. When these sources of underground water outlets are designed and located without proper site investigation, water related diseases such as cholera, typhoid, water rashes etc. could be prevalent. According to (Augustine, 2011) water borne diseases are the leading causes of death in Nigeria.

Little or no attention has been given to leach pit as a possible pollution source in Nigeria perhaps due to ignorance or insensitivity of

both the people and the government. Hence, extensive hydrological information becomes necessary to develop water resources and protect them especially underground water reservoirs. Leach pit system have been the traditional way to dispose storm water and domestic waste from buildings. Leach pits are seen increasingly as a more widely applicable option alongside either means of ground water control and disposal. Leach pit must store the immediate storm water runoff and allow for its efficient infiltration into the adjacent soil. They must discharge their stored water sufficiently quickly to provide the necessary capacity to receive run-off from a subsequent storm. The time taken for discharge depends upon the leach pit shape and size, and the surrounding soils infiltration characteristics.

As a general guideline, it is recommended that the bottom of the pit should be at least 2m

above the ground water level and a minimum horizontal distance of 30m between a pit and a water source is normally recommended to limit exposure to microbial contamination source (India Standard Code of Practice for Sanitation). Shallow hand dug wells may have their water contaminated by nearby leach pits. To avoid contamination, it is expedient that wells must be deep and sunk far away from latrines and refuse disposal points. The extent to which compliance to standard is achieved the safer for water consumers of underground sources.

Table 1 showed national regulations on safe distances to safe water in some parts of the world. Unfortunately, no value was accepted for Nigeria. The values range from 0 to 100 meters.

Table 1: National Regulations on the safe distance between latrines and water points

S/N	Country	National Standard	Legal Instrument
i.	Bangladesh	15 meters	Bangladesh National Building Code, 1993
ii.	Burkina Faso	25 meters	Article 34
iii.	Ethiopia	50 meters	Ministry of Health, 2004
iv.	Ghana	50 meters	Community Water and Sanitation Agency of Ghana
v.	Mali	15 meters	00
vi.	Mozambique	50 m (Private Well) 30 m (Govt. Well)	Low-Cost National Sanitation Programme
vii.	South Africa	100 meters	00
viii.	Uganda	50 meters	00
ix.	Nigeria	00	00
x.	India	00	00
xi.	Malawi	00	00
xii.	Madagascar	00	00
	United State Environment al Protection Agency (USEPA)	15 meters	00

Source: Department for International Development (DFID): Dew Point, Enquiry No. A030

The distance decay effect is to the extent that all things are related but near things are more related than far things (Tobler, 1970). This tends to set limit to human movement and some patterns of spatial organization. This common phenomenon of space economy of distance decay is clearly discernable in explaining the interaction between a leach pit and a hand dug well in terms of distance separating them. The tendency here is that the shorter the distance separating the source of ground water from a well, the more the level of pollution and vice-versa, all other factors being held constant. The safe distance from a leach pit and a well is represented by about 8 days travel of the ground water.

Most studies on shallow ground-water normally concentrate on depth and water chemistry for example, Fabiyi, (2008) examined the depth of hand dug wells and water chemistry in Ibadan North East Local Government Area of Oyo state, Nigeria. He concluded that coliform count, pH, total hardness, iron and chlorine increase with increasing depth while nitrate and bicarbonate reduce with depth. He suggests chlorine as most important chemical parameter that is related to well depth. Since ground water is a product of geological formations, some studies examined ground water quality in relation to influence of geology in urban environment. Nwafor et al (2013) analyzed the seasonal influence in the physico-chemical concentrations in hand dug wells in Akure town noted that of the parameters studied, pH, total dissolved solids, total alkalinity, potassium, iron, sulphate have higher concentrations in the wet season. Whereas, temperature, turbidity, total hardness, chloride, magnesium, electrical conductivity, sodium, nitrate have higher concentrations in the dry seasons.

Oyeku and Eludoyin (2010) assessed heavy metal pollution of ground water resources in Ojota Area of Lagos metropolis noted that hand dug wells and boreholes near Olusosun landfill were contaminated with heavy metals. The uncontrolled disposal of lead and batteries, spent petroleum products probably caused the relatively high level of lead, copper and iron in ground water. These trace metals are dangerous because they tend to bio-accumulate resulting in heavy metal poisoning (Abolude et al, 2009). Imoisi et al, (2012) examined the impact of municipal wastes on the quality of ground water in Benin City and found concentration levels of physico – chemical and bacteriological loading higher in wells close to dumpsite than those far away.

Danmo et al, (2013) in Bama and Konduga towns in Borno State in Sudanosahelian ecological zone, noted that nitrate, manganese, faecal coliform concentrations in both hand-dug wells and boreholes were above the WHO permissible limit for drinking water. Nwankwoala and Udom (2011) found ground water to be acidic, high chloride concentration linked to saltwater intrusion and high iron content in the wells in the Eastern part. The import of this is that bacteriological and physico-chemical properties in relation to distance are relevant factors in determining the quality of water.

THE STUDY AREA

The study area for this research is Ilorin South Local Government with Fufu as its headquarters. Ilorin is the headquarters of Kwara state in the North Central zone of Nigeria.

Ilorin South is one of the three local governments in Ilorin Metropolis

Figure 1: Map of Ilorin South Inset Map of Kwara State and Ilorin Metropolis
Source: DivaGIS.org, country spatial Data base 2020

Figure 1: Relief of Ilorin South
Source: DivaGIS.org, country spatial Data base 2020

Ilorin is located between Latitude $8^{\circ} 30'$ and $8^{\circ} 30'$ North of the equator and between Longitude $4^{\circ} 20'$ and $4^{\circ} 35'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian (see figure 1). Ilorin is the gateway city between the Southern and Northern Nigeria with an approximate land area of 100-kilometer square.

Ilorin has wet and dry climate. The tropical air mass from the Atlantic Ocean starts from March to October, while the tropical continental air mass from Sahara Desert begins from November to February (Olaniran, 2002). These respective air masses results into the usual eight months rainy season of double maxima rainfall pattern reaching its peak in June and September, and the four months dry season. The annual rainfall of Ilorin is an average of 1500 mm. The minimum temperature ranges from 21.1°C to 25°C while the average maximum temperature is 38°C . The Relative Humidity stands at 77.5% and a daily sunshine of 7.1h (Olawaju, 2009). This climatic variation was in tandem with the findings of (Ajibade and Ojelola, 2004).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data for this study were obtained from both primary (field observations) and secondary sources from the archival materials. The primary data was sourced through the conduct of direct personal interview. Water samples were taken within the study area and distance measurements were taken from leach pits to the hand dug wells within the study area. The measurements of the distances were carried out on the field with the aid of line tape.

The secondary data were sourced from different regulatory guidelines institutions on water quality. National regulations were obtained from Department for International Development (DFID). Data on physical properties was obtained from World Health Organisation (WHO). Data on permissible conductivity,

magnesium, turbidity and TDS levels were obtained from Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON). Safe distance regulations were obtained from United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). Nitrate admissible limit was obtained from National Primary Drinking Water Standard (NPDWS).

On the whole, five political wards were sampled out of the eleven wards of the study area. These wards are: Akanbi, Balogun Fulani, Budo-Efo, Okaka and Oke-Ogun wards. Four of these wards are urbanized while only one (Budo-Efo) is a rural ward. A buffer zone of a diameter of 30 meters was created around the areas surrounding each leach pit. Hence, shallow wells lying within this buffer were isolated for sampling. Water samples were collected in plastic water bottles and preserved at low temperature to reduce the effect of physical and chemical reactions. The water samples were taken to the laboratory on the same day of collection. As water samples were collected, distances to the shallow wells were also taken using measuring tape. Sampling was further repeated 2 times after the incident occurrence.

Data were collected in the 5 wards of the study area namely: Akanbi, Balogun Fulani, Budo-Efo, Okaka and Oke-Ogun wards. These samples were collected in the study area 2 times in June and July of 2019.

Two data analysis methods were used in this study. First, is the laboratory analysis which produced the data obtained on the water samples through laboratory test (Table 2). The second one is the statistical method of descriptive and analytical types.

Altogether, 12 chemical parameters were tested in this study. The tests were carried out at the Chemistry and Microbiology laboratory respectfully of University of Ilorin. A detail of the laboratory method is presented in Table 2.

The methods adopted were taken after APHA, et al, (1993) and Fawole and Osho (2007) (1998), (2001), Ademoroti, (1999), Handershot

Table 2: Procedures and Methods of The Physico-Chemical and Bacteriological Investigations
Source: APHA (1998) ; APHA (2001) ; Ademoroti (1999) ; Handershot et al (1993) ; Fawole and

S/ N	Test	Methods and Procedures
1.	pH	Water pH was determined by using a pre-caliberated pH meter using ammonia buffer 4,7,9 solution.
2.	Total hardness	This was analyzed by titration of 25ml of water sample with standard Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA) using Erichrome as indicator.
3.	Chloride (Cl)	This was determined using MOHR method.
4.	Electrical conductivity	A stabilized digital conductivity meter calibrated using potassium chloride standard solution was used to determine electrical conductivity.
5.	Calcium (Ca)	This was performed by complexometric titration with EDTA.
6.	Magnesium (mg)	We pipette 25ml of mg (NO ₃) ₂ stock solution into a clean and dry 250ml Elenmeyer flask.
7.	Nitrate	50ml of water sample was measured into a 250ml Erlenmeyer flask and added mercury chloride (II) to get concentration of 1000mg/l. We used spectrophotometer at absorbance 420nm to measure Nitrate.
8.	Turbidity (ftu)	This was determined using a turbidity meter.
9.	Total dissolved solids	Filtration method was used.
10.	Total Coliform Counts	Serial Dillusion Technique (SDT) was used.
11.	Total Viable Counts	Serial Dillusion Technique (SDT) was used.
12.	Feacal Coliform Counts	Serial Dillusion Technique (SDT) was used.

Osho (2007)

Both descriptive and inferential were used for analysis and interpretation of the variables. The analytical techniques employed were Pearson product moment correlation at 0.05, two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) at a benchmark of three components extraction.

FINDINGS

(i) AVERAGE DISTANCE OF LEACH PITS TO HAND DUG WELL AND LEVEL OF COMPLIANCE TO STANDARD

Table 3 present the relative distances of leach pit to the nearest well in the study area. In Akanbi ward, well 1 was 8.5 meters to the leach pit, while the highest was in well 5 with 31 meters to the leach pit. In Balogun Fulani, with the exception of well 1 with 11.5 meters, all the wells were greater than the 15 meters average distance adopted by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). At Budo-Efo, all the wells were greater than the 15

meters stipulated by USEPA. The situation became pathetic in Okaka ward where all the wells are 15 meters and below. This condition becomes more pathetic in view of the fact that Okaka is located in the Central Business District (CBD)

One notable concern in this area is that it is traversed in close proximity by the Asa River where heaps of landfills along the banks of the river constitutes a possible point source of groundwater pollution. There is incidence of violation of effective distance between the wells and the leach pits in this area which may constitute a major health risk factor. In Okeogun ward, well 1 and well 2 were 4.8 meters and seven meters respectively below the prescribed USEPA standard of 15 meters. This is what was also obtained in Okaka ward. This is detrimental to health especially because of the closeness of the two wards to Asa River. Wells 3, 4 and 5 with 18 meters, 23 meters and 32 meters respectively were however met the USEPA standard.

Table 3: Pattern of Average Distance in Meters between Water Well and leach Pits

S/N Ward	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5
1. Akanbi	*8.5	15.5	21	27	31
2. Balogun Fulani	*11.5	25.5	27	28	50
3. Budo-Efo	18	20.5	21	24.7	33
4. Okaka	*6	*12.2	*13	15	23
5. Oke-Ogun	*4.8	*7	18	23	32

** Below WHO minimum standard*

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

(II). PATTERN OF WATER CHEMISTRY OF SHALLOW WELL IN ILORIN SOUTH

(a) PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF WATER

(i.) pH

The results presented in Table 4 showed that pH values were within acceptable standard of WHO in Okaka ward. Also, in Oke-Ogun ward with the exception of well 3 all the other values of pH were acceptable. pH values in Budo-Efo were completely below the acceptable standard of 6.5 for all the sampled wells. In Balogun Fulani ward, values were below acceptable standard in well 2 in the first sample and the average value and all others were within the acceptable standard. In Akanbi ward, all the values were below the acceptable standard except in well 2 in the first sample and in the average value. pH is important to the Chemistry of water. It affects tastes, hardness and therefore affects the uses of water. The water becomes acidic; it will be contaminated with pollutants and corrodes or dissolve metal pipes. The study revealed that the pH of the water in Akanbi ward were all virtually lower than 6.5mg/l except in well 2.

In Balogun Fulani ward, only well 3 falls in the above category while all the wells in Budo-Efo ward are lower than 6.5mg/l but none was recorded to be lower than this minimum threshold in Okaka and Oke-Ogun wards. According to Nkansah et al, (2010), pH values lower than 6.5mg/l are considered too acidic for human consumption and can cause health problems such as acidosis having adverse effects on digestive and lymphatic system of humans. However, all the wells in Okaka have pH higher than 7mg/l except in well 3 while only well 2 falls into this category in Oke-Ogun ward. The pH

values of water in the study area are generally within weak acids and weak alkalis. The lowest being 5.9mg/l and highest 7.4. 76% of the water (19 wells) are acidic while 20% (5 wells) are alkaline and only 4% (1 well) is neutral.

The essence of the PH which scale range from (0-14mg/l) is to determine the medium of acidity or alkanity of the water hence, the pH value is important in water purification. The pH in the study area is slightly acidic in nature. This may be attributed to the anthropogenic activities among other causes. The limit of pH value for drinking water is specified as 6.5gm/l – 8.5mg/l (WHO 2004) and India Standard Specification (ISI 1993).

(ii) Water Hardness

Values of water hardness were generally acceptable except in Oke-Ogun ward where the values are generally high. The same was also recorded for well 5 in Okaka ward. Water hardness affects the foaming of soap, it causes formation of lime scale in kettles and water heaters. It also causes cardiovascular diseases. The total hardness in the study area, 24% of the samples (6 wells) were beyond the WHO permissible limits with Oke-Ogun ward recording the highest of between 548mg/l and 608mg/l concentration level while the remaining 76% of the samples (19 wells) falls within the standard. The water in the study area was generally moderately hard.

However, for specific calcium concentration in the sampled water, 56% (14 wells) exceeded the permissible limits of drinking water quality in

Balogun Fulani, Okaka and Oke-Ogunwards in ascending concentration level between 92.92mg/l and 142.7mg/l while the remaining 44% (9 wells) falls within permissible limit of drinking water quality. The water exhibited very high level of magnesium concentration, all of which were far above the permissible limits with Budo-Efo having the lowest followed by Akanbi ward from 58.8-107.5 respectively. Highest concentration was recorded in Oke-Ogun from 405.4mg/l -478.1mg/l followed by Okaka 270.3mg/l -393.9mg/l and Balogun Fulani 315-381mg/l.

The total hardness increased as the level of calcium and chlorine increased. The increasing level of calcium and magnesium are largely responsible for the water hardness. Water concentration of 0-75mg/l is soft, 75-150mg/l is moderately hard and 150-300mg/l is very hard. The analytical results of the total hardness indicated that water in the study area is hard to moderately hard and the hardness is due to the presence of some particulate matters.

(iii) Turbidity

All the values of turbidity were below the required standard. This is due to the fact that hand dug well is being used. All the water samples in the study area exhibit a lower tolerable degree of turbidity below 5(ntu) which is the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) maximum permissible limit. The level of turbidity increases with increasing hardness in the study area with Oke-Ogun and Okaka wards having the highest level of turbidity ranging from 2.13-3.32(ntu). Budo-Efo ward recorded the lowest of 0.05-0.25(ntu) followed by Akanbi ward 0.72-0.98(ntu) and Balogun Fulani 1.87-

2.11(ntu). Turbidity is haziness or cloudiness of water. It is also related to the content of disease-causing organisms in water, which may come from soil runoff. In other words, turbidity in drinking water is caused by particulate matter that may be present from source water.

(iv) Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Dissolved minerals in water are referred to as TDS. They are compounds of calcium, magnesium and sodium. The values of the TDS were generally acceptable in all the wards. The TDS changes the mineral content of the water, which is important to survival of many animals. Also, dissolved salt can dehydrate the skin of aquatic animals, which can be fatal. It can increase the temperature of the water which many animals can survive in. High TDS can result in water having a bitter or salty taste, result in incrustations, films or precipitates on fixtures, corrosion of fixtures and reduced efficiency of water filter and equipment. Calcium and Magnesium minerals commonly found in TDS, can cause water hardness, scale formation and staining. Extremely low concentrations of TDS may also be unacceptable. The water samples in the study area recorded relatively low amount of total dissolved solids (TDS), the lowest being 107mg/l and the highest of 298mg/l as against the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) permissible limit of 500mg/l. Oke-Ogun ward has the highest of TDS concentration of between 280-299mg/l.

The results of the pH, acidity/alkalinity and TDS in the study area were in tandem with the studies of Adam et al, (2013) where these parameters were found to be lower in quartzite

area than those of granite schist and gneiss area of Kano. This also conforms with the chemical and bacteriological analysis of hand dug wells in Makurdi town by Tse and Adamu (2012) in which the water was found to be moderately hard with low TDS. High TDS may cause gastro intestinal irritation. High TDS presence in water decreases the quality and affect the taste of water. It is important to know that the pH determine the suitability of water for various

uses such as drinking, bathing, cooking, washing, agriculture etc. While pure water is neutral at pH of 7, it is acidic below pH of 7 and alkaline at pH above 7. Turbidity on the other hand is caused by wide variety of suspended particles. Excessive hardness in water however makes conductivity to be high. Variations of TDS in groundwater are contamination from anthropogenic sources (Marghade et al, 2010).

Table 4: Result of physico-chemical properties of the 1st and 2nd samples collected in June and July, 2019.

	Well	PH			Hardness mg/l			Chloride mg/l			Conductivity Us/cm			Calcium mg/l			Nitrate mg/l			Magnesium mg/l			Turbidity (NTU)			TDS mg/l		
		1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv	1 st	2 nd	Mv
Akanbi Ward	A1	6.3	6.2	6.3	134.40	130.20	132.3	48.21	48.921	48.6	40.12	40.10	40.1	32.06	40.10	31.3	10.10	10.20	10.2*	102.34	99.74	101.04*	0.844	0.845	0.85	128	130	129
	A2	6.5	6.4	6.5	105.00	117.60	111.3	42.54	43.958	42.8	40.00	40.04	40.02	28.86	40.04	29.7	9.80	9.60	9.7	76.14	87.14	81.64*	0.718	0.719	0.72	122	125	124
	A3	6.4	6.3	6.4	142.80	134.40	138.6	43.95	44.66	44.3	40.27	40.28	40.03	30.86	40.28	30.9	10.30	10.30	10.3	111.94	103.56	107.75*	0.984	0.980	0.98	136	139	138
	A4	6.2	6.2	6.2	88.20	84.00	86.1	46.08	45.37	45.7	32.88	32.90	32.9	21.64	32.90	21.7	9.60	9.70	9.7	66.56	62.26	64.41*	0.831	0.832	0.83	133	135	134
	A5	6.1	6.2	6.2	92.40	94.50	93.5	48.21	47.50	47.9	33.50	33.55	33.5	28.65	33.55	38.8	8.90	8.80	8.9	63.55	65.68	64.62*	0.824	0.822	0.82	130	132	131
Balogun Fulani Ward	B1	6.5	6.6	6.6	462.00	453.60	458	248.15	247.44	247.8*	42.92	42.93	42.9	97.80	42.93	98.18*	19.10	19.00	19.1*	364.20	355.05	359.6*	2.114	2.114	2.11	156	158	157
	B2	6.4	6.4	6.4	415.80	420.00	418	246.73	247.44	247.1*	42.56	42.53	42.6	94.59	42.53	94.58*	18.50	18.60	18.6*	321.25	325.44	323.4*	1.880	1.882	1.88	150	153	152
	B3	6.6	6.6	6.6	420.00	430.50	425	219.79	218.72	219.3*	42.80	42.78	42.8	81.76	42.78	81.77*	17.80	17.60	17.7*	338.24	348.72	343.5*	1.942	1.940	1.94	155	154	155
	B4	7.0	6.9	7.0	394.80	420.00	407	194.97	194.26	194.4	42.40	42.43	42.4	92.98	42.43	92.92*	16.30	16.30	16.3*	301.82	327.15	314.5*	1.865	1.866	1.87	148	145	147
	B5	6.4	6.5	6.5	451.50	441.00	446	163.07	163.07	163.1	42.90	42.90	42.9	65.73	42.90	65.77	18.20	18.20	18.2*	385.77	375.20	380.5*	2.102	2.100	2.10	152	150	151
Budofo Ward	C1	6.1	6.0	6.1	77.70	84.00	80.9	32.61	33.32	36.97	32.60	32.50	32.55	17.64	32.50	17.7	8.00	8.20	8.1	60.06	66.32	63.2*	0.228	0.223	0.23	117	117	117
	C2	6.3	6.4	6.4	88.20	84.00	86.1	39.70	39.70	39.7	32.80	32.80	32.80	27.25	32.80	27.3	8.40	8.30	8.4	60.95	56.70	58.8*	0.184	0.180	0.18	115	116	116
	C3	6.1	6.2	6.2	92.40	94.50	93.5	51.75	51.04	51.4	33.60	33.58	33.59	16.03	33.58	16.1	9.20	9.10	9.2	76.39	78.43	77.4*	0.248	0.244	0.25	119	120	120
	C4	6.2	6.2	6.2	88.20	79.80	84	45.37	46.08	45.73	32.80	32.82	33.81	19.24	32.82	19.2	8.10	8.20	8.2	68.96	60.60	64.8*	0.048	0.050	0.05	110	111	111
	C5	5.9	5.8	5.9	66.20	66.20	66.2	42.54	43.24	42.89	30.90	30.96	30.93	16.08	30.96	16.1	7.90	7.90	7.9	50.12	50.15	50.1*	0.104	0.102	0.10	108	107	108
Okaka Ward	D1	7.2	7.1	7.2	474.60	472.60	473.6	255.54	255.24	255.2	42.95	42.94	42.95	109.00	42.94	109.00*	19.00	19.00	19.00*	365.60	363.48	364.5*	2.542	2.540	2.54	164	164	164
	D2	7.3	7.3	7.3	357.00	369.60	363.3	170.16	170.16	170.2	41.52	41.54	41.53	92.98	41.54	92.97*	17.90	17.80	17.85*	264.02	276.64	270.3*	2.126	2.125	2.13	168	169	169
	D3	7.0	7.0	7.0	441.00	445.20	443.1	195.68	194.97	195.3	42.90	42.88	42.89	107.41	42.88	107.38*	19.00	18.90	18.95*	333.59	337.86	335.7*	2.380	2.380	2.38	180	182	181
	D4	7.1	7.1	7.1	420.00	428.40	424.2	194.26	93.55	193.9	42.80	42.80	42.80	129.85	42.80	129.83*	18.00	18.10	18.05*	290.15	298.60	294.4*	2.340	2.342	2.34	165	167	166
	D5	7.4	7.3	7.4	533.40	533.40	533.*4	221.90	221.20	221.5	42.96	42.99	42.98	139.47	42.99	139.47*	18.20	18.30	18.25*	393.93	393.93	393.9*	3.106	3.103	3.11	279	280	280
Oke-Ogun Ward	E1	6.6	6.5	6.6	546.00	550.20	548*	242.47	241.06	241.8	44.10	44.12	44.11	142.68	44.12	142.7*	18.40	18.40	18.4*	403.32	407.56	405.4*	3.114	3.115	3.11	294	293	294
	E2	7.1	7.1	7.1	609.00	606.90	608*	226.17	225.46	255.8*	44.80	44.85	44.83	129.86	44.85	129.9*	19.30	19.40	19.4*	479.14	477.00	478.1*	3.324	3.322	3.32	299	298	299
	E3	6.5	6.4	6.5	583.80	583.80	584*	225.46	226.17	255.8*	44.42	44.40	44.41	134.67	44.40	134.7*	18.30	18.40	18.4*	449.20	449.12	449.2*	3.318	3.316	3.32	296	298	297
	E4	6.7	6.7	6.7	567.00	575.40	571*	255.24	256.65	255.9*	44.14	44.16	44.15	131.46	44.16	131.5*	18.70	18.60	18.7*	435.54	443.90	439.7*	3.294	3.298	3.30	295	294	295
	E5	6.7	6.6	6.7	592.20	588.00	590*	263.74	265.16	264.5*	49.59	44.60	47.1	137.87	44.60	137.9*	19.10	19.00	19.1*	454.33	450.16	452.2*	3.320	3.320	3.32	298	298	298
WHO Limits			6.5-8.5			500			200			1000 (SON)			75			10(NPD WS)			50			5 (SON)			500 (SON)	

MV= Mean Value

*Value above standard

Source: Author's Field Conceptualization, 2019

WHO = World Health Organization

SON = Standard Organization of Nigeria

NPDWS = National Primary Drinking Water Standard

(b) CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF WATER

(i) Chloride

In the study area, the chloride concentration of the water was high in 10 of the sampled wells above WHO permissible limits amounting to 40% of the total, while the remaining 15 well samples forming the balance of 60% met the recommended standard permissible limits for drinking water quality. Oke-Ogun and Balogun Fulani wards recorded the highest of between 225.8mg/l -264.5mg/l and 163.1mg/l -247.8mg/l respectively. The chloride values were all within acceptable limit in Akanbi and Budo-Efo wards. It was generally high in Balogun Fulani ward except in wells 4 and 5. Also, the values were high in wells 1 and 5 in Okaka ward while others are within acceptable standard. All the values in Oke-Ogun ward were generally high above the required drinking water standard.

Well water high in chloride can give drinking water an unpleasant taste. Chloride increases the electrical conductivity of water and thus increases its corrosivity. It reacts with metals to form soluble salt thus increasing the levels of minerals in drinking water. Its elevated concentration can be toxic to some aquatic life. High chlorine concentration was the hallmark in the works of Adebo et al, (2009) in the aquifers of Lagos. The excess of chloride in the water is usually taken as an index of pollution and is considered as tracer from ground water contamination (Loizidou and Kappetanious1993).

(ii) Nitrate

All the nitrate values in Budo-Efo and Akanbi wards were within acceptable standard except in well 1 of Akanbi ward. The values were generally high in Balogun Fulani, Okaka and Oke-Ogun wards. Nitrate is an important source

of Nitrogen for plant and animal life. High nitrate has health effects as increased heart rate, nausea, headache and abdominal cramps. There is generally high concentration of Nitrate in the sampled water in the study area above the National Primary Drinking Water Standard (NPDWS) which set the Minimum Contaminant Level (MCL) for Nitrate at 10mg/l (measured as Nitrogen). 68% of the sample water have Nitrate concentration of 10mg/l or more in 17 wells with Oke-Ogun ward taking the lead from 18.4mg/l -19.4mg/l followed by Okaka ward 17.85mg/l -1900mg/l, Balogun Fulani 16.3-19mg/l.1, Akanbi ward 8.9-10.3mg/l and Budo-Efo has the lowest of between 7.9-9.2mg/l while the remaining 8 wells about 32% are below.

The high level of nitrate concentrations in a significant number of wells in the study area beyond the NPDWS agrees with the findings of the study by Edet et al, (2011) covering the sedimentary basins of Benin, Benue, Niger Delta and Sokoto crystalline basement complexes. This is an indication of anthropogenic pollution. High degree of nitrate and chlorine concentration also forms part of the findings of Adebo and Adetoyinbo et al, (2009) in unconsolidated aquifers of Lagos exceeding WHO guide limit for drinking water, Nwankwoala and Udom (2011) in Niger Delta and Adelana et al, (2003), (2004) and (2005) in the Southeastern part of Lagos where these

parameters were of objectionable proportion in all the wells.

These were linked to salt intrusion and shallow depth of the wells. Fabiyi (2008) in his studies of water chemistry in Ibadan Northeast suggested chlorine as most important chemical related to well depth. This finding was also justified in the study Olatunji et al, (2015). High nitrate content was also discovered in water quality study by the World Health

Organization (WHO) in 2010 in the Democratic Republic of Timorleste.

(iii) Calcium

The calcium concentrations in Akanbi and Budo-Efo wards were all within acceptable standard of WHO. It was however generally high in Okaka, Oke-Ogun and Balogun Fulani wards except in its well 5. Calcium is an important determinant of water hardness, and also functions as a pH stabilizer because of its buffering qualities. It also gives water a better taste. The findings of Emeka Chima Ogoko (2019) found calcium among other parameters to exceed their permissible limits. Higher calcium content can cause abdominal ailments and is undesirable for domestic uses as it causes encrustation and scaling (WHO 2004).

(iii) Magnesium

All the wells in wards exhibit very high values of magnesium. It was much higher in Balogun Fulani, Okaka and Oke-Ogun wards than Akanbi and Budo-Efo wards all of which are not within acceptable standard. Drinking water in which magnesium is present in high concentrations can have a laxative effect. It causes water hardness in combination with calcium though not health risk but a nuisance because of mineral builds up on fixtures and poor soap or detergent performance. Rahanian et al, (2015) carried out the analysis of physiochemical parameters to evaluate the drinking water quality in the state of Perak, Malaysia, magnesium was found to be below the standard maximum concentrations of recommended limits of WHO and the National Drinking Water Quality Standard (NDWQS).

(iv) Conductivity

Conductivity determines how much dissolved substances, chemicals and minerals are present in water. The more the impurities in water the

higher the conductivity more the harm it could cause to human. In the study area, the level of conductivity of water is low ranging from 30.93mg/l to 47.11mg/l. this showed that the level of impurities in the water is low and the permissible maximum limit of 1000mg/l set by the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON). Concentration, types and temperature of ions solution affects conductivity (Ham, 1985).

(c) BACTERIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF WATER

The results of the bacteriological properties showed that the values of total coliform and viable counts in all the wards were not within acceptable standard. E-Coli was detected in well 5 in Okaka ward. E-Coli is a bacterial in human feces which could cause bloody diarrhea, severe anemia, kidney failure and urinary tract infection. The presence of E-Coli in well 5 in Okaka ward may not be unconnected with the availability and closeness of cow dumps and indiscriminate littering of human feces. Isah et al, (2015) in examining the water quality assessment of dug wells in Lagos Island observed significant level of coliform contamination in wells dug around toilets. According to WHO (2010), numerous epidemiological studies and outbreak investigations globally have found a direct association between poor water quality and infectious diarrhea.

COMPONENTS OF SHALLOW GROUNDWATER CHEMISTRY

Principal Component Analysis was used for analysis and interpretation of the variables computed in each of the wards. For Akanbi ward (Table 4a), the dominant parameters were: mg+ (46.1%), distance, (32.6%) and chloride (16.5%) and cumulative explanation of 96.2% of the variance. In Balogun Fulani ward (Table 4b), TDS has the highest loading and explanation of 43.6 %. TVC also loaded

highly with an explanation of 29.6%, while, Ca^{2+} have an explanation of 15.2%. These 3 components cumulative explained 88.4% of the variance in shallow groundwater chemistry of Balogun Fulani. In Budo-Efo ward (Table 4c), chloride with the highest load explained 58.6% of the variance, TDS contributed 25.9%, while pH had a contribution of 11.6%. cumulatively they all explained 96.1% of the water

chemistry of shallow groundwater in Budo-Efo. In Okaka ward (Table 4d), Mg^{2+} dominated the explanation with 46.1%, TCC also was with 32.6% explanation and NO_3^- with 16.5%, all these cumulatively contributed 95.2% explanation. In Oke-Ogun ward (Table 4e), Cl^- dominated the explanation with 58.6%, Ca^{2+} with 25.9% and pH with 11.7% and altogether, they contributed 96.1% explanation to the variance.

Table 4(a): Factor Analysis of the Correlation Matrix with Distance in Akanbi Ward

	Rotated Component Matrix		
	1	2	3
Distance	0.319	0.851	0.157
pH	0.337	0.436	-0.788
Hardness	0.900	0.281	0.334
Chloride	-0.384	0.463	0.797
Conductivity	0.870	0.085	0.437
Calcium	-0.582	0.745	0.323
Nitrate	0.497	0.110	0.826
Magnesium	0.984	-0.153	0.094
Turbidity	0.971	0.207	0.119
TDS	0.412	0.224	0.789
TVC	0.027	-0.951	-0.137
TCC	-0.110	0.980	0.149
Total Eigen Value	5.5	3.9	2.0
% of Variance	46.1	32.6	16.5
Cumulative %	46.1	78.7	96.2

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 4 (b): Factor Analysis of the Correlation Matrix with Distance in Balogun Fulani Ward

	Rotated Component Matrix		
	1	2	3
Distance	-0.134	-0.979	-0.079
pH	0.359	0.045	0.905
Hardness	0.359	-0.114	0.419
Chloride	0.152	0.075	0.050
Conductivity	0.861	-0.520	0.414
Calcium	-0.063	0.172	-0.951
Nitrate	0.800	0.253	0.096
Magnesium	0.898	-0.196	-0.023
Turbidity	0.822	0.466	-0.133
TDS	0.966	0.193	-0.137
TVC	0.064	0.995	0.031
TCC	-0.014	0.975	0.126
Total Eigen Value	5.2	3.5	1.8
% of Variance	43.6	29.6	15.2
Cumulative %	43.6	73.2	88.4

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 4 (c): Factor Analysis of the Correlation Matrix with Distance in Budo-Efo Ward

	Rotated Component Matrix		
	1	2	3
Distance	0.926	0.201	0.234
pH	0.052	0.375	-0.913
Hardness	0.558	0.827	0.031
Chloride	0.932	0.273	0.050
Conductivity	0.523	0.610	0.593
Calcium	-0.020	0.930	0.180
Nitrate	0.797	-0.079	0.480
Magnesium	0.898	-0.196	-0.023
Turbidity	0.386	0.898	-0.203
TDS	-0.960	0.096	0.255
TVC	-0.879	-0.424	0.175
TCC	0.059	0.893	-0.427
Total Eigen Value	7.6	3.4	1.5
% of Variance	58.6	25.9	11.6
Cumulative %	58.6	84.5	96.1

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 4 (d): Factor Analysis of the Correlation Matrix with Distance in Okaka Ward

	Rotated Component Matrix		
	1	2	3
Distance	0.319	0.851	0.157
pH	-0.337	0.435	-0.788
Hardness	0.900	0.281	0.334
hloride	-0.384	0.463	0.797
Conductivity	0.870	-0.085	0.437
Calcium	-0.582	0.745	0.323
Nitrate	0.497	0.110	0.826
Magnesium	0.984	-0.153	0.094
Turbidity	0.971	0.207	0.119
TDS	0.412	0.224	0.789
TVC	0.027	-0.951	-0.137
TCC	-0.110	-0.980	0.149
Total Eigen Value	5.5	3.9	1.9
% of Variance	46.1	32.6	16.5
Cumulative %	46.1	78.7	95.2

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 4 (e): Factor Analysis of the Correlation Matrix with Distance in Oke-Ogun Ward

	Rotated Component Matrix		
	1	2	3
Distance	0.926	0.201	0.234
pH	0.052	0.375	-0.913
Hardness	0.558	0.827	0.031
Chloride	0.932	0.273	0.050
Conductivity	0.523	0.610	0.593
Calcium	0.020	0.930	0.180
Nitrate	0.797	-0.079	0.480
Magnesium	0.702	0.685	-0.028
Turbidity	0.386	0.898	-0.203
TDS	0.029	0.892	0.375
TVC	-0.879	-0.424	0.175
TCC	0.059	0.893	-0.427
Total Eigen Value	7.6	3.4	1.5
% of Variance	58.6	25.9	11.7
Cumulative %	58.6	84.5	96.1

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Hence, the pollutants vary in their concentration from one ward to the other the dominant parameters are: mg+, distance, cl-, TVC, ca+, TDS, pH, TCC, No3-. These clearly showed that 8 out of 12 chemical parameters largely defined the chemistry of shallow groundwater in the study area.

The results of the correlation analysis showed that TCC and TVC decrease in concentration with distances from shallow walls, while other parameter mostly increased in their concentrations with distances from wells. This is expected because TCC and TVC are pollutant injected and sourced from the soak-away. Other non-biological pollutants are mainly derived from the chemical quality of the over burden rock (Table 5(a), (b), (c), (d), (e)).

RELATIONSHIP WITH WATER CHEMISTRY AND DISTANCE FROM LEACH PIT

Table 5 (a): Relationship between Distance to leach pit and Groundwater Quality in Akanbi Ward

S/N	Samples	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5	WHO Standard
	Distance	8.5m	15.5m	21m	27m	31m	
1.	PH	6^	6.5	6.4^	6.2^	6.2^	6.5-8.5mg/l
2.	Hardness	132.3	111.3	138.6	93.5	86.1	500 mg/l
3.	Chloride	48.6	42.8	44.3	47.9	45.7	200 mg/l
4.	Conductivity	40.1	40.02	40.3	33.5	32.9	1000 mg/l
5.	Calcium	31.3	29.7	30.9	28.8	21.7	75 mg/l
6.	Nitrate	10.2*	9.7	10.3*	8.9	9.7	10 mg/l
7.	Magnesium	101.04*	81.64*	107.75*	64.62*	64.41*	50 mg/l
8.	Turbidity	0.85	0.72	0.98	0.82	0.83	5ntu
9.	TDS	129	124	138	131	134	500 mg/l
10.	TVC	7.6*	4.6*	4.1*	4.1*	3.5*	0mpn/100ml
11.	TCC	5.6*	3.4*	2.5*	1.4*	2.3*	0 mpn/100ml
12.	FCC	00	00	00	00	00	0 mpn/100ml

---- No Growth

^Below WHO minimum standard

TDS-Total Dissolved Solid

TVC-Total Viable Counts

* Above WHO minimum standard

TCC-Total Coliform Counts

FCC-Fecal Coliform Counts

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 5 (b): Relationship between Distance to leach pit and Groundwater Quality in Balogun Fulani Ward

S/N	Samples	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5	WHO Standard
	Distance	11.5m	25.5m	27m	28m	50m	
1.	PH	6.6	6.5	6.4 [^]	7.0	6.6	6.5-8.5mg/l
2.	Hardness	425	446	418	407	458	500 mg/l
3.	Chloride	219.3*	163.07	247.1*	194.6	247.8*	200 mg/l
4.	Conductivity	42.8	42.9	42.6	42.4	42.9	1000 mg/l
5.	Calcium	81.77*	65.77	94.58*	92.92*	98.18*	75 mg/l
6.	Nitrate	17.7*	18.2*	18.6*	16.3*	19.1*	10 mg/l
7.	Magnesium	343.5*	380.5*	323.4*	314.5*	359.6*	50 mg/l
8.	Turbidity	1.94	2.10	1.88	1.87	2.11	5ntu
9.	TDS	155	151	152	147	157	500 mg/l
10.	TVC	5.8*	7.1*	6.3*	5.1*	3.5*	0mpn/100ml
11.	TCC	5.0*	4.7*	4.7*	3.4*	2.6*	0mpn/100ml
12.	FCC	00	00	00	00	00	0mpn/100ml

---- No Growth

[^]Below WHO minimum standard

TDS-Total Dissolved Solid

TVC-Total Viable Counts

* Above WHO minimum standard

TCC-Total Coliform Counts

FCC-Fecal Coliform Counts

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019.

Table5 (c): Relationship between Distance to leach pit and Groundwater Quality in Budo-Efo ward

S/N	Samples	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5	WHO Standard
	Distance	18m	20.5m	21m	24.7m	33m	
1.	PH	6.4 [^]	6.2 [^]	5.9 [^]	6 [^]	6.2 [^]	6.5-8.5mg/l
2.	Hardness	86.1	93.5	66.2	80.9	84	500 mg/l
3.	Chloride	39.70	51.40	42.89	32.97	45.73	200 mg/l
4.	Conductivity	32.80	33.59	30.93	32.55	33.81	1000 mg/l
5.	Calcium	27.3	16.1	16.1	17.7	19.2	75 mg/l
6.	Nitrate	8.4	9.2	7.9	8.1	8.2	10 mg/l
7.	Magnesium	58.8*	77.4*	50.1*	63.2*	64.8*	50 mg/l
8.	Turbidity	0.18	0.25	0.10	0.23	0.05	5ntu
9.	TDS	116	120	108	117	111	500 mg/l
10.	TVC	7.2*	7.0*	6.9*	5.1*	3.6*	0mpn/100ml
11.	TCC	5.7*	5.3*	5.3*	3.1*	2.3*	0 mpn/100ml
12.	FCC	00	00	00	00	00	0 mpn/100ml

---- No Growth

[^]Below WHO minimum standard

TDS-Total Dissolved Solid

TVC-Total Viable Counts

* Above WHO minimum standard

TCC-Total Coliform Counts

FCC-Fecal Coliform Counts

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 5 (d): Relationship between Distance to leach pit and Groundwater Quality in Okaka Ward

S/N	Samples	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5	WHO Standard
	Distance	6m	12.2m	13m	15m	23m	
1.	PH	7.3	7.1	7.0	7.4	7.2	6.5-8.5mg/l
2.	Hardness	363.3	424.2	443.1	533.4*	473.6	500 mg/l
3.	Chloride	170.2	193.9	195.3	221.5*	255.2*	200 mg/l
4.	Conductivity	41.53	42.80	42.89	42.98	42.95	1000 mg/l
5.	Calcium	92.97*	129.83*	107.38*	139.47*	109.01*	75 mg/l
6.	Nitrate	17.85*	18.05*	18.95*	18.25*	19.00*	10 mg/l
7.	Magnesium	270.3*	294.4*	335.7*	393.9*	364.5*	50 mg/l
8.	Turbidity	2.13	2.34	2.38	3.11	2.54	5ntu
9.	TDS	169	166	181	280	164	500 mg/l
10.	TVC	6.7*	7.6*	6.5*	6.1*	4.5*	0mpn/100ml
11.	TCC	5.5*	5.2*	5.0*	3.6*	3.2*	0mpn/100ml
12.	FCC	00	00	00	1.0*	00	0mpn/100ml

---- No Growth

*Above WHO minimum standard TDS-Total Dissolved Solid TVC-Total Viable Counts

TCC-Total Coliform Counts FCC-Fecal Coliform Counts

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

Table 5 (e): Relationship between Distance to leach pit and Groundwater Quality in Oke-Ogun Ward

S/N	Samples	Well 1	Well 2	Well 3	Well 4	Well 5	WHO Standard
	Distance	4.8m	7m	18m	23m	32m	
1.	PH	6.6	7.1	6.7	6.5	6.7	6.5-8.5mg/l
2.	Hardness	548*	608*	571*	584*	590*	500 mg/l
3.	Chloride	241.8*	225.8*	255.9*	255.8*	264.5*	200 mg/l
4.	Conductivity	44.11	44.83	44.15	44.41	47.1	1000 mg/l
5.	Calcium	142.7*	129.9*	131.5*	134.7*	137.9*	75 mg/l
6.	Nitrate	18.4*	19.4*	18.7*	18.4*	19.1*	10 mg/l
7.	Magnesium	405.4*	478.1*	439.7*	449.2*	452.2*	50 mg/l
8.	Turbidity	3.11	3.32	3.30	3.32	3.32	5ntu
9.	TDS	294	299	295	297	298	500 mg/l
10.	TVC	7.8*	5.7*	5.5*	6.1*	2.9*	0mpn/100ml
11.	TCC	5.0*	4.4*	4.2*	3.9*	1.6*	0 mpn/100ml
12.	FCC	00	00	00	00	00	0 mpn/100ml

---- No Growth

* Above WHO minimum standard TDS-Total Dissolved Solid TVC-Total Viable Counts

TCC-Total Coliform Counts FCC-Fecal Coliform Counts

Source: Author's field conceptualization, 2019

CONCLUSION

The presence of bacterial in water in the study area may cause outbreak of cholera, dysentery, typhoid and yellow fever with further consumption of the well water when not adequately treated. Other diseases such as stomach and intestinal illness like nausea which might lead to death are also likely. High chloride in water may have laxative effects, while high TDS may cause gastro intestinal irritation. The high TDS presence in water also decreases the quality and affects the taste of water. pH determines the suitability of water for various purposes such as drinking, bathing, cooking, washing, agriculture etc. The study revealed that TVC and TCC as the most strongly varied with distance from leach pit. These play an important role in the water quality.

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